

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Gore**FIRST NAME:** Jasunella**PROGRAM CODE:** DIPH**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 24-26)
3. American against British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-35)
4. The Turabian Style (EUCLID 2021, 44-55)
5. Font variation (EUCLID 2021, 3-4)
6. Headings/ subheadings (EUCLID 2021, 36- 43 & 52-52)
7. Contractions (EUCLID 2021, 12)

THE ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

I have always thought I was able to write in English relatively well. This comes from being a native English speaker, whereby daily I am interacting with individuals in English, writing English, complying reports, and so on. In addition, I recently completed a master's degree in the UK, where I had to write strict British English. However, on reading the coursepack, I realized I have quite a bit to learn. This presented a challenge to me, I had to read and re-read the coursepack several times to ensure that I understood the grammatical rules. Questions and doubts arose as I started wondering if I would be able to adjust to this new style. Would I be able to catch-up and not fall behind in attempting to get my work of a high standard? How does it compare to my experience and knowledge?

Despite this course appearing daunting at first, I realized this would only make to improve my writing skills. I can only get better if I am able to challenge and push myself. This course provides the medium to continue to develop and grow as a writer. Throughout the rest of this paper, I will seek to explore the points I have found to be integral to my development.

2) THE ACADEMIC ESSAY

In the university setting, essays are a common assignment. Academic essays are evidence-based ideas used to influence a reader (Kain 1999). Therefore, in writing these essays I need to be able to convince my readers about a particular topic, based on the evidence available.

The initial chapter of the coursepack explores the essay writing process. One of the points that really resonated with me was the importance of starting early. This would allow the writer the time to do background research, process the information, and write (EUCLID 2021, 1). Ongoing through this first chapter, I realized this is indeed an integral aspect to the success of essay writing. The various components of the essay include reading; then re-reading with notetaking; organizing the research information and ideas in order to help formulate the research question; planning how to go about answering the formulated question; first draft; editing of first draft to ensure it contains all the necessary points and that it has a certain flow to it; and writing of the final paper (EUCLID 2021, 1-4). All these components will take time and the writer would have to dedicate sufficient time to each stage to achieve a propelling essay.

In addition, throughout the writing process, the writer must be a creative and a critical thinker. Creative is defined as “marked by the ability or power to create; given to creating” (Merriam-Webster’s Dictionary, n.d.). Therefore, the ability to think “outside the box” would help in looking at a question in a different way and come up with unique solutions. The coursepack mentions brainstorming and mind mapping as two techniques that would help the writer in their creativity (EUCLID 2021, 2). I have previously heard of the techniques, but never fully delved into what each one signifies and how it would contribute to my skill as a writer. This course gave me the opportunity to explore these techniques a little deeper. Looking at different examples of brain mapping I thought it was an excellent way to involve the more creative side of me into the research process. Mind mapping involves developing one’s idea through visual cues that would help dissect a topic, breaking down the different aspects and drawing relationships (Monah University 2020). Looking at examples of the different brain maps, I realized they ranged from extravagant to very simple. However, I can see how this would assist me in breaking down complex topics, making it easier for me to understand.

The other aspect involves critical thinking. Critical is defined as “inclined to criticize severely and unfavorably” (Merriam-Webster’s Dictionary, n.d.). Although, this definition appears harsh, within the academic writing process critical thinking is necessary. I have learnt both through this coursepack and through experience, that critical thinking allows you to ask questions. Only through critically appraising the existing information/research can I find gaps in the knowledge and seek to answer these questions. Only then can I make a significant contribution to research and academia on a whole.

3) THE STYLE GUIDE

This is the first time I have encountered “style guide.” I always thought that if something is written “properly” then that was acceptable. According to the coursepack “a style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2021, 24). Due to the different rules within the English language that can be controversial from one author to the next, I can see the importance of having a guide that an author can follow to maintain consistency.

It was brought out that the style guide is essential for certain writers, these include business, commercial, technical, news (newspaper, radio, television), web copywriters, and so on. Even if there are multiple writers working on a project, with the use of the style guide, it would not be noticeable where one person’s work end to where another begins.

One of the styles that was mentioned was the *BBC News style guide*. On further evaluation of this style, I discovered that they had guidelines not only on how words are to be spelt, but also included: how to write numbers; grammar and the use of punctuation; use of military terms; the use of names of places and individuals; how to write about religion in a culturally sensitive manner; and so on. These very extensive set of guides are to ensure that the standard of the stories that the BBC produce are of the highest quality (BBC 2020).

I believe this is an essential tool, I find having a guide relieves some of the burden and stress in producing a paper. However, the only issue that I foresee is that authors need to be able to be adaptable to different style guides, especially if they were freelance writers. For an individual managing more than one style guide at a time, I can see room for confusion. As in my circumstance, I was accustomed to writing a certain way, however, entering this course, I realized that I needed to change a lot of what I knew to adapt to what was required. This I find was time-consuming, slow and a challenging process. Despite, these issues I can see that the skills I would have learnt would aid in my formation as a writer.

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

As the influence of the U.S. increases around the world, the American English has become the authority in the English language (EUCLID 2021, 27). British English is the oldest version of English that exist. In the sixteenth century the British started introducing English to the Americas. However, in the U.S. a man called Noah Webster as a sign of independence from Britain was instrumental in most of the changes made to the British English, converting it to American English (British Council: Indonesia Foundation 2021). Since then, we have various versions of the English as it spread from region to region around the world (e.g., Australian, Caribbean, Indian, Canadian, etc.). As indicated by the coursepack, for the purpose of the course the American English should be used.

I have been known to interchange both the American and British English. This is because of having strong influences from both areas. My country was originally a colony

of Britain and to this day we pay homage to the queen. My primary and secondary education centered around the use of British English. Recently I did my master's degree in the UK, and they were strictly British English. On the other hand, my country is in close proximity to the U.S., and we do have a lot of interactions with them. This has therefore, impacted my English as well. In my post I am often put in the position where I must write multiple reports and as they are directed toward the U.S. I sometimes find myself writing the American version. Therefore, without even realizing it, I have been interchanging the two.

Throughout the coursepack, I found several examples of both the American and the British English. For instance, in the first chapter, words such as “analyse,” “organise,” “centre,” “familiarise,” and “significance” can be considered British spelling of words. Meanwhile, in chapter two, words such as “offense”, and “author” are more consistent with the American style spelling. Another example of the discrepancy between the two would be the use of inverted commas consistent with the British style vs quotation marks of the American style. An example of this can be found in the use of inverted comma on page ten (‘bibliography’ and ‘references’) (EUCLID 2021, 10), meanwhile on page 13 they reverted to using quotation marks (“however,” “Nevertheless,” etc) (EUCLID 2021, 13). These inconsistencies can be seen throughout the entire document.

Recognizing the different styles did take some effort. At first, I was not sure what would be considered British as opposed to the American style. It took not only careful studying of the coursepack but extensive reading and research to be able to begin to grasp the differences. I understand that consistency throughout my paper is important, and I must try as much as possible to use the rules of spelling, punctuation, and grammar within the American style of writing.

5) THE TURABIAN STYLE

The Turabian style was first created in 1937 by Kate L. Turabian based on the Chicago style (MacMillan 2011, 2). It was originally made for students that were working on papers that would not be published. Rules were adjusted so that it excludes information needed for publishing books (Fleming 2018). One of the main features that distinguish between the two styles is the use of numbering for notes. The Turabian style uses superscripts meanwhile Chicago style uses a number in parenthesis (Hege Library & Learning Technologies 2021). According to many other sources there are other differences, but the main difference is one previously mentioned.

The Turabian style also encompasses the way a paper should be written. This includes the layout, font size, margins, in-text citations, references, use of titles, subheadings and so on. The coursepack also suggest additional reading (e.g., Chicago Manual of Style, Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations) in case of any questions or doubts during the writing process. This I believe would be extremely helpful as I attempt to learn this style.

I have always been accustomed to the American Psychological Association (APA) format and have used it in most of my papers. The APA format began in 1929, used mainly for psychology, education, and social science papers (Cherry 2020). One of the main differences I noticed was the use of footnotes within the Turabian. I must admit that the use of footnotes makes the writing process a little easier. Especially, when at the end of writing this paper, references were so easily generated. Before, I would have to use a separate word document to assist me in ensuring that my reference list was complete, but here the computer does most of my work for me.

I knew there were other styles, but never really explored any of them. This course has given me the opportunity to open my horizons and learn another style. My main concern, however, was whether or not the Turabian style would be difficult to adjust to. However, as I delve further into this style, I realize that although it carries some differences to the APA format, there is still a good many similarity. I would still need some time to adjust but with the course materials and internet sources, I believe I would soon be fluent.

6) ERRORS

I briefly wrote about some of the inconsistencies I noticed within the coursepack as it pertains to the use of the British vs American English. In this section, I will seek to expound a little further on the other errors I detected. Based on the coursepack these errors are intentional for the purpose of helping students like myself to learn. I hope through this discourse that I have touched the main ones.

a) Font variation

Throughout the coursepack, I was able to identify two different fonts. The first was Time News Roman in the first few chapters and then converted to Calibri in the last two. In addition, there were font size variations within the text. Some chapters use point 12 font, others used 11.5 and there was also 11-point font. I would understand if these variations were there to add emphasis to points in the material, however, these changes were not just for a sentence or two but for entire chapters at a time.

It has been recommended that use of multiple fonts be limited because it could distract from the paper. It can show a piece of work to be unprofessional and disorganized (Badich 2017). In addition, according to the University of New England, when it comes to writing essays it strongly prohibited to change fonts (University of New England 2021, 1). This I have found to be true, in my post as an adjunct professor, one of the things I was told to penalize students for, was the use of multiple fonts. I know it comes into play when trying to show emphasis within the text or to illustrate the thoughts of a different author.

This material was written by different authors; therefore, I contributed the change of font to the preference of the individual authors. However, after reading about style guide within the coursepack, I was wondering if that came into play for this paper. Where the authors given freedom to choose the different fonts or was this intentional?

b) Missing Headings/ Subheadings

Apart from the role of headings in conveying key concepts, they also play a role in organizing concepts within a paper (Elite Editing 2020). In chapter seven of the coursepack, there were two different papers, however there was no separation between the two stories. This made it difficult transitioning from one paper to the next. The first essay revolved around the financial crisis of the U.S. that would affect the world economy, then without any indication the second essay began which spoke about the curriculum vitae (CV). A heading indicating the change would have made it easier to follow the material and appreciate the difference between the two authors.

During the first paragraph of the second essay, I realized this had to be a completely different essay as there was no connection to the previous paper. The train of thought was different as they focused on two very different topics. The use of footnotes was used in the first essay which was discarded in the second essay. The second author opted for using the author's name and date in parenthesis after the in-text citation. Both methods were correct according to the Chicago/ Turabian style, but multiple times throughout the coursepack it has been emphasized the importance of consistency.

c) Use of contractions

According to the coursepack, contractions should never be used (EUCLID 2021, 12). However, within the first chapter there were multiple contractions used (e.g., can't, don't, and you're). Contractions are considered informal speech, but academic writing is considered formal, therefore, contractions can be considered inappropriate. Although, in certain circumstances it can be used: in the case of direct quotation; use of idioms; describing of contractions; writing informal speech within your paper (Lee 2015).

I must admit to using contractions on multiple occasions. Therefore, now being re-acquainted to informal against formal speech, I now will have to be conscious of my use. Even writing this paper I had to review it several times to ensure that I did not use contractions. To my dismay I had a few, for which I had to correct.

7) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401 period one (1) coursepack made me re-analyze all I knew about the English language. It has shown me, that I need to be more mindful when I am writing, taking into consideration all the necessary adjustments that I need to make. Moving away from the British English to the American English is one of the adjustments I need to pay careful attention too. With the assistance of the coursepack and all the available aids would help in improving my writing.

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